

Complementary Figures

1. Study Search and Selection Process

Figure 1. Study search and selection process

2. A research themes classification procedure from the primary studies

Figure 2. A research themes classification procedure from the primary studies

3. Publication venues

Figure 3. Publication venues

4. Challenges reported by the primary studies over the years

Figure 4. Challenges reported by the primary studies over the years